

Science Teams Gender Composition and Online Visibility in Latin America and the Caribbean via OpenAlex and Altmetrics

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Abstract

Gender equality remains a central issue in global scientific development, with women comprising approximately 30% of the global research workforce. Addressing disparities in gender representation in science teams is vital to fostering inclusivity and driving scientific innovation. This study investigates the relationship between gender composition in science teams and online visibility in Latin America and the Caribbean (LAC), leveraging OpenAlex bibliometric data and Altmetric Attention Scores (AAS). Our research questions focus on whether gender composition influences online visibility and whether differences exist across gender-balanced and gender-skewed teams. Analyzing 138,123 articles from 2013 to 2022, we classified teams based on women ratio and assessed visibility metrics across scientific domains. Results reveal no significant correlation between gender composition type of science teams and online visibility overall, although domain-specific analyzes in social and physical sciences teams suggest subtle variations influenced by groups of gender composition. These findings contribute to ongoing debates on gender diversity and scientific performance, highlighting the need for more granular analyzes of gender dynamics, leadership roles, and interdisciplinary contexts. Future work should expand geographic coverage and integrate traditional citation metrics to deepen insights into the gender-performance relationship.

Introduction

Gender equality is a pivotal issue in the global development agenda (United Nations, 2022). In science, women account for ~30 percent of the global scientific workforce (UNESCO UIS, 2019) and a forecast estimates gender parity in author leadership positions in 258 (*sic*) years in physics (Holman et al., 2018). Understanding these disparities is crucial for fostering a more inclusive and equitable scientific community, which is essential for driving innovative ideas and the progress of science (Kozłowski et al., 2022; Sugimoto & Larivière, 2023).

Science teams are one scenario where women's increasing participation can enhance the scope and impact of research. Science teams are the driven force in modern science because of its virtue of leveraging and blending diverse capabilities of individuals (Wu et al., 2019). A research hotspot among the science of team science (SciTS) (National Research Council, 2015) is the relationship between team gender composition and performance (Bell et al., 2011; Li et al., 2023; Wallrich et al., 2024).

The epistemic community of SciTS has produced a stream of research on teams' gender composition, women/men's leadership, gender roles, and its relationship with scientific impact and innovativeness (e.g., Hajibabaei et al. (2022), Kozłowski et al. (2022), Liu et al. (2022), Yang et al. (2022)). While there has been significant scholarly work on science team gender composition and performance (Li et al., 2023), most studies have prioritized investigating in the contexts of high-income countries, sourcing data from canonical bibliographic databases such as Scopus or WoS which tend cover fewer academic contributions of academics from the Global South (Visser et al., 2021).

We position our contribution within the literature on gender composition in scientific teams and their performance by leveraging comprehensive bibliographic databases such as OpenAlex (OpenAlex, 2023; Visser et al., 2021). Our study incorporates online visibility metrics (i.e., ‘altmetrics’ (Altmetric, 2024a)) as indicators of performance and focuses on Latin America and the Caribbean (LAC)—a region facing funding and personnel constraints but gradually shifting toward a research-oriented scientific workforce (UNESCO, 2010; Vasen et al., 2023). This study seeks to answer the following research questions:

RQ₁: Is there a relationship between the gender composition of LAC-science teams and their online visibility?

RQ₂: Are there differences between the gender composition of LAC-science teams and their online visibility?

Methodology

Data

OpenAlex and LAC-science teams. OpenAlex is a comprehensive and open catalog that encompasses the entire global research system. It has indexed over 200 million research outputs, including papers, authors, institutions, and journals from around the world (OpenAlex, 2023). We analyzed articles published by LAC-based science teams over a 10-year period (2013–2014). These teams are defined as groups of 2 to 10 co-authors, where over 50% have their primary affiliation with institutions in LAC. The team size of 2–10 members follow the consensus standard established by the National Research Council (2015).

Gender inference. We used the World Gender Name Dictionary for gender inference already assessed and used in large bibliometric analyzes (Zhao et al., 2023). This dictionary employs a probabilistic approach to infer gender based on first names. It integrates regional and linguistic variations alongside statistical probability score (Martínez et al., 2021).

Online visibility. We sourced the Altmetric Attention Score (AAS) as a measure of online visibility. The AAS is a composite indicator which measures the attention received by academic research across diverse platforms, including mainstream media, social media, policy documents, patents, post-publication peer reviews, and online reference managers. AAS is an integer calculated based on factors like the reach and influence of each mention and the credibility of the source (Altmetric, 2024b). We sourced the AAS for each OpenAlex article via its Digital Object Identifier (DOI).

Final sample. After excluding LAC-science teams with at least one member whose gender could not be inferred or without AAS data, our final sample comprised 138,123 OpenAlex articles (Figure 1).

Figure 1 Data collection, LAC-science teams, and gender inference

Grouping gender composition.

We computed the women ratio in each LAC-science team as follows: $women\ ratio = \frac{n\ women}{total\ n\ team\ members}$. Then, we consider the following composition intervals to group LAC-science teams by women ratio composition:

- *Men-Majority Teams* = $women\ ratio \leq 0.2$ (~35% of the LAC-science teams)
- *Men-Driven Teams* = $0.2 < women\ ratio < 0.4$ (~17%)
- *Gender-Balanced Teams* = $0.4 \leq women\ ratio \leq 0.6$ (~13%)
- *Women-Driven Teams* = $0.6 < women\ ratio < 0.8$ (~14%)
- *Women-Majority Teams* = $women\ ratio \geq 0.8$ (~19%)

Results

Concerning our *RQ1*: *Is there a relationship between the gender composition of LAC-science teams and their online visibility?* Figure 2 reports the Spearman rank correlation results controlled by scientific domains (i.e., Life Sciences, Social Sciences, Physical Sciences, and Health Sciences). Spearman correlation values are in general weak or near zero. This shows no significant correlation between the gender ratio of LAC-science teams and AAS, regardless of their scientific domain.

Figure 2 Spearman correlation between women ratio and AAS by scientific domain. Note: small-scale research teams: 2-4 members; medium-sized research teams: 5-7 members; large-scale research teams: 8-10 members.

Concerning our *RQ2*: *Are there differences between the gender composition of LAC-science teams and their online visibility?* Figure 3 shows no noticeable differences across domains, suggesting comparable score distributions. Yet, the median AAS of the Men-majority team in all domains except physical sciences seems to be higher than the other gender composition teams. Figure 4 presents that the social sciences (Gender-Balanced Teams vs. Men-Driven Teams, $p < .05$ — Men-Driven Teams vs. Women-Driven Teams, $p < .05$) and physical sciences (Men-Driven Teams vs. Women-Driven Teams, $p < .05$ — Gender-Balanced Teams vs. Women-Majority Teams, $p < .05$) domains have the strongest evidence of gender-composition effects based on the post-hoc Dunn's test results.

Figure 3 Distribution of AAS score for each type of gender composition science teams and scientific domain.

Figure 4 p-values from Dunn's tests for each type of gender composition science teams and scientific domain.

Discussion and conclusions

This research in progress aimed to examine the relationship between the gender composition of LAC-science teams and their performance measured as online visibility, and to investigate whether differences exist based on gender composition. Our results did not find evidence of gender composition and online visibility in LAC-science teams. Yet, the post-hoc Dunn's

reveals that certain gender composition types of LAC-science teams have a significant association on online visibility in both the social sciences and physical sciences, in line with previous research by Yang et al. (2022) which shows that mixed-gender teams' leads to higher performance, in specific domains, such as medical sciences. Yet, the lack of systematic relationships and differences across scientific domains and team size and online visibility underscores inconsistent findings discussed elsewhere. For instance, gender diversity in research and development (R&D) teams has yielded contradictory findings in relation to performance. While a negative effect of gender diversity has been observed on teams' performance measured as applications, no significant impact has been found on patents if they apply for international protection (Teruel & Segarra-Blasco, 2022). Future research should further explore the mechanisms that drive online attention and investigate how gender intersects with other variables, such as team power dynamics and leadership, to shape the visibility and impact of scientific research. Additionally, the inclusion of more countries and the contrast with traditional hybrid indicators (i.e., citation and production) can enrich the insights presented and discussed here.

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